

'82 Update—Composite Manufacturing Technology

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ABSTRACT

It appears that the decade of the 80's will represent a dramatic transition period in manufacturing technologies as they apply to composites. This transition is being driven by two powerful new driving forces:

- 1) Entry of these materials into high volume components - particularly in the automotive industry.
- 2) The fact that composite components in almost all industrial applications have become lower in cost than components made from traditional materials.

This latter event has taken these products out of the Specialty Industry category and made them part of the Commodity Industries. These driving forces impact the manufacturing of composite capital equipment in two primary ways: the first is represented by a great deal more emphasis on specialty machinery as opposed to well known and accepted generic equipment, i.e. filament winders, pultrusion machines, and tape placement machines, etc. The second is the requirement to invest in automation equipment for production of composite end products in exactly the same manner that investments would be made in manufacturing equipment for high volume production of traditional material end products. All of this should tend to accelerate the growth of the composite industry providing other barriers, such as: engineering education, existing traditional manufacturing equipment, and philosophical bias can be overcome.

This paper will deal with some specific examples of this trend that are currently visible.

TEXT

Originally born into the aircraft industry; an industry of relatively low volume and where performance overrides economics as the prime criteria - composite products, over the past thirty years, have essentially been relegated

to the premium cost, specialty performance marketplace. However, events of the last decade have brought about socio-economic changes worldwide that have precipitated a reversal of this trend. During this decade a number of new factors have come into play that will allow composite products to be competitive with, and even less costly than, products that were made from the traditional materials they replace. And, by the way, you still get all those unique properties as a fringe benefit.

This change has been brought about primarily by the increase in energy costs, beginning with the oil embargo and the extortion techniques that were taught by OPEC to the Bauxite-producing nations. The resulting steep rise in raw-metal ingot costs, together with a much flatter curve occurring in composite raw materials, has created a situation where, on a performance basis, the raw-material costs that affect the price of composites are less than those of traditional metal components.

RAW MATERIAL COSTS

	Price/lb.
ROVINGS	.68
RESIN (POLYESTER)	.62
COMPOSITE	.71
ALUMINUM	.76
STEEL INGOT	.25
SPECIFIC ALUMINUM	1.06
SPECIFIC STEEL	1.12

The 1974 oil embargo created a whole new set of ground rules. Energy became expensive and the energy intensive processing of steel and aluminum forced both raw material and finished goods prices to escalate dramatically.

ENERGY CONTENT-TRADITIONAL METALS

	MJ/KG
STEEL (SHEET)	29
ALUMINUM (SHEET)	175
ALUMINUM (DIE CAST)	90

During this same period composite prices climbed on a flatter curve as a result of the very considerably lower energy content of these materials.

ENERGY CONTENT-GLASS FIBER *

	MJ/KG
ROVING	43
CHOPPED STRAND MAT	52
CHOPPED STRANDS	44
WOVEN ROVING	46
YARN	63

* Source of Energy Content Figures - British FRP Magazine, International Reinforced Plastics Industry (November 1981)

ENERGY CONTENT-RESINS

	MJ/KG
POLYESTER	92
EPOXY	167
PHENOLIC	82
POLYAMIDE	190
POLYCARBONATE	146

ENERGY CONTENT-COMPOUNDS

	MJ/KG
BMC, 18% GLASS/52% FILLER	44
SMC, 30% GLASS/35% FILLER	54
POLYAMIDE, 30% GLASS	153
POLYCARBONATE, 30% GLASS	126
POLYPROPYLENE, 30% GLASS	107

ENERGY CONTENT-PROCESSES

	MJ/KG
CONTACT MOLDING	1.8
SPRAY-UP	1.4
HOT PRESS MOLDING	4.4
SMC	5.8
PULTRUSION	4.2
FILAMENT WINDING	1.4

ENERGY CONTENT-PRODUCT

	MJ/KG
CONTACT MOLDED	82
SPRAYED-UP	80
HOT PRESS MOLDED	88
SMC	60
PULTRUDED	58
FILAMENT WOUND	80

Having reached this important milestone, it is therefore clearly evident that if the conversion costs can be equal to or less than those for metals, the end product is bound to be significantly less expensive.

Because of their specialized (and therefore short-run) nature, little attempt has been made over the years to develop a high-volume automated production processing system for composite materials. However, it is self-evident that if these materials are going to enter the high-production areas, specialized processes and machinery must be developed--exactly as was done in the metal fabricating industry.

Although we are still languishing at the bottom of the evolutionary curve, it is nonetheless obvious some significant advances have already been made in this area, resulting in some startling cost comparisons between composites and other materials of design in high-volume structural parts, particularly for automotive applications.

Lets take a look at a specific example in the automotive industry that demonstrates the substantially lower costs of the composite unit when compared with its traditional steel counterpart. A process for the totally automated manufacture of leaf springs for the automotive, railroad, electrical, industrial and sporting goods industries was developed by Goldsworthy Engineering, Inc. under the trademark Pulformer™.

With this type of processing equipment the lower-cost raw materials can be converted at considerably lower labor costs.

LABOR COSTS

COMPOSITE

SINGLE STEP PROCESS

FULLY

SEMI SKILLED LABOR

STEEL

MULTIPLE

SEMI AUTOMATED

SKILLED & SEMI SKILLED LABOR

Materials and labor savings in the production of automotive leaf springs are far from the only manufacturing economies resulting from the change from steel to composites in this application.

FACILITY COSTS

FLOOR SPACE

STEEL 100,000 Sq.Ft.

COMPOSITE 6,000 Sq.Ft.

CAPITAL EQUIPMENT

STEEL \$6,000,000

COMPOSITE 400,000

BASELINE - ANNUAL CAPACITY

3,000,000 Units

MFG. HAZARD RELATED COSTS

INSURANCE

WORKERS COMPENSATION

MANUFACTURING ENVIRONMENT

THESE COSTS ARE ALL SUBSTANTIALLY HIGHER IN THE MANUFACTURE OF STEEL SPRINGS DUE TO THE NEED TO HANDLE HOT MATERIALS.

POLLUTION CONTROL COSTS

IN TODAY'S ENVIRONMENT THE COST OF CONTROLLING THE POLLUTION OF A MANUFACTURING PROCESS MAY EVEN EXCEED THE COST OF THE BASIC CAPITAL EQUIPMENT. AS COMPARED TO STEEL COMPOSITE SPRING PROCESSING IS ALMOST POLLUTION FREE.

CASCADING EFFECT ON FINAL PRODUCT

LIGHTER WEIGHT AND BETTER DAMPING CHARACTERISTICS PRODUCE A CASCADING COST SAVING EFFECT IN THE AUTOMOBILE. I.E. SMALLER SHOCK ABSORBERS, ETC.

CONSUMER SAVINGS

IN THE TRANSPORTATION INDUSTRY EVERY POUND SAVED IN TRUCK WEIGHT IS A POTENTIAL INCREASE IN PAYLOAD. REDUCTION IN MAINTENANCE COSTS AND DOWN TIME INCREASE PROFITS. COMPOSITE SPRINGS CONTRIBUTE SUBSTANTIALLY IN BOTH THESE AREAS.

Even though these figures show the composite spring to be ahead in virtually every area, these results are only valid when process optimization and manufacturing automation occur. This means that achieving these results requires capital expenditure just as it would in setting up a new manufacturing operation for producing this product in traditional materials. Fortunately, as illustrated earlier, even these capital costs tend to be substantially lower in composites than in steel.

The automotive leaf spring constitutes an excellent example of the economics and performance of a composite part in head on competition with traditional materials, but it is far from an isolated example. Additional auto-

motive applications as well as products for many diverse industries continue to substantiate the trend.

Automotive drive shafts produced continuously on this highly automated piece of equipment represent another case where composites (graphite-fiber glass epoxy hybrid) permit product economical gains as well as upgraded performance. Although the material cost of the hybrid are relatively high, the manufacturing economies and the ability of the composite shaft to operate full span, without need for midspan bearings and universal joints, lower end product costs.

Specifically designed for making automotive window frames and employing a new processing technology with elements of both pultrusion and compression molding this piece of capital equipment is another in the new generation of

volume composite product producers. Although originally dedicated to window frames this unit is capable of the automatic production of a wide variety of structural parts (i.e. bumpers, seat frames, transmission supports, etc.)

Abuse resistant, high strength, single piece structural panels for the intermodal container and truck/trailer industries are manufactured continuously on this machine. Capable of composite facing plywood on both sides in widths up to ten feet and at rates exceeding sixty square feet per minute in any length panel this production system provides a highly cost effective structural panel to the transportation industries.

Replacing what were essentially hand layup techniques this machine manufacturers graphite/epoxy golf shafts continuously at the rate of approximately

one shaft per minute. To permit the production of a broad range of shaft stiffnesses and lengths the machine can be programmed to alter the wind angle of individual graphite plies to vary both torsional and longitudinal stiffness as well as actual and wall thickness taper and length.

The ability to erect large diameter tankage on site with unskilled labor and low volume, low density materials points up another avenue for cost reduction and superior performance when compared to traditional materials and construction methods. The system employs a pultrusion machine housed in a standard forty foot trailer van to produce a hollow, liquid tight, structural profile designed to specific tank requirements. A sufficient length of this profile to provide the desired tank diameter and height is pultruded. This profile is wound into a storage canister and then back fed into the tank wall by the erection machine. This machine helically winds the interlocking profile, continuously bonding the interlocking surfaces until the finished tank wall is achieved.

These examples of the new "cheaper and better" stature of the composites industry would seem to bode well for accelerated growth of our industry through the balance of the eighties and beyond. However, barriers to both long and short term acceptance of these materials into the commodity market are manifest. Even within the industry itself realization of this new role is not universal. Given this situation, the magnitude of educating the rest of the industry, where probably not more than two out of five know the meaning of the word, seems overwhelming. Now, the pluses are with us. Technical people throughout the industry are convinced that composites will enhance their product lines and even management is using these materials as public relations fodder to pitch their future image.

All of this adds up to an exciting challenge to all of us in the industry. An opportunity to play a prominent role in furthering the progression along the evolutionary curve toward the upcoming Composites Age.